

ANYTIME ALGORITHM TO GENERATE NON-DOMINATED VECTORS TO BI-OBJECTIVE INTEGER PROGRAMMING PROBLEMS

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Abstract: *In this study we address the bi-objective mixed-integer programming problems. Our solution approach is an adaptation of a general procedure proposed in the recent literature to solve multiple objective optimization problems. The integrality of the decision variables generates a discrete Pareto front that is not easy to be fully disclosed using a framework developed for continual problems. We combine the manner of defining and ordering the sub-sets of the Pareto front (from the continual approach) with a new way of choosing hypothetical bounds to be targeted (specific to the integer optimization problems). We carried out experiments on bi-objective knapsack, and integer problems. Preliminary results show that the proposed approach performs well in comparison to the results reported in the literature.*

Keywords: *Multiobjective optimization, combinatorial problem, anytime algorithm*

1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper we propose an anytime solution algorithm to bi-objective mixed-integer programming (2objMIP) problems that is able to generate well distributed vectors on the Pareto front, and report the numerical results of our experiments carried out on bi-objective knapsack problems (2objKP), and an integer programming (2objIP) problem. Within experiments we used Octave programming language and its GLPK solver for all single objective linear optimizations.

Generally, multiple objective (MOIP) problems are widely studied in the recent literature. See for instance (Toloo et al., 2022), (Domínguez-Rios et al., 2021) and (Cai et al., 2019). The state of art and main challenges in solving multiple objective combinatorial problems can be found in (Ehrgott et al., 2016). The so called anytime algorithms are those algorithms that produce a valid (0-level approximation) solution even when they are interrupted before they finish. The quality of the solution derived by such algorithms must be directly improved with the time the algorithms run. In our context: (i) the exact solution (i.e. the Pareto front of a 2objMIP problem) is a set of points, and its 0-level approximation means any of its subsets; (ii) the quality of the approximate solution increases with the running time if and only if, whenever the execution of the algorithm stops, a set of well distributed points along the exact set is yielded. See (Domínguez-Rios et al., 2021) for more details.

(Ehrgott et al., 2016) provided a wide survey of the exact methods to solving multiple objective combinatorial optimization (MOCO) problems. (Deb and Miettinen, 2009) provided a review of nadir point estimation procedures based on evolutionary approaches. They discussed the dimensionality reduction issue. We recall an example from (Ozpeynirci and Koksalan, 2010) where an exact algorithm for finding extreme supported nondominated points to multiple objective mixed integer programs was introduced.

Our algorithm is essentially based on the TDM model introduced in (Stanojevic and Glover, 2020) to solve multiple objective continual problems. We propose a variant of this algorithm, obtained by exploiting the particularity of discrete Pareto front of MOIP problems. The original TDM model was formulated with the help of a hypothetical bound defined as a convex combination of certain already generated non-dominated vectors.

Our algorithm, C-TDM, generates an approximation to the Pareto front of the bi-objective continual problem, namely the problem obtained by ignoring the integral constraints, and use the vectors from that approximation as hypothetical bounds in the integer form of the classic TDM model. C-TDM can be easily adapted to be used in a more general context.

Our paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the basic notation and terminology; Section 3 briefly describes the specificity of our solution approach, while Section 4 reports some of our numerical results. The final conclusion and some directions for further researches are included in Section 5.

2. PRELIMINARIES

The general model of a multiple objective optimization (MOO) problem is given in (1).

$$\max_{x \in X} (f_i(x))_{i=\overline{1,p}}, \quad (1)$$

where $p \geq 2$ is the number of objectives, $X \subseteq R^n$ is the feasible set of the decision variables $x \in R^n$, and $f_i : X \rightarrow R, i = \overline{1,p}$ are the objective functions that all have to be maximized. Particular models are obtained from (1) by imposing various special conditions on variables, feasible sets, and/or objective functions.

Let $F : X \rightarrow R^p$ be defined by $F(x) = (f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_p(x))$. The image of the feasible set in R^p defined by $F(X)$ represents the criterion space. The main concept used in defining solutions to MOO problems is the concept of dominance.

A feasible solution $x' \in X$ is said to dominate another feasible solution x'' – written $F(x') \geq F(x'')$ – if $f_i(x') \geq f_i(x'')$ for all $i \in M$. Further on, x' strictly dominates x'' if and only if x' dominates x'' and in addition $f_i(x') > f_i(x'')$ for at least one index $i = \overline{1,p}$. A feasible solution is called Pareto optimal or Pareto efficient if there is no feasible solution that strictly dominates it.

A vector/point from the criterion space is called non-dominated if it is the image of a Pareto optimal solution. The set of all non-dominated vectors of an MOO problem represents the Pareto front. For more details we refer the reader to (Pardalos et al., 2017).

PESA algorithm was proposed in (Stanojevic and Glover, 2020) to provide a pattern efficient approximation to the Pareto front of a general MOO problem. It used the TDM optimization model that we recalled here in its simplified form

$$\max \left\{ \sum_{i=\overline{1,p}} c_i f_i(x) + p_0 \lambda \mid x \in X, f_i(x) \geq \lambda y_i^0, i = \overline{1,p}, \lambda \geq 0 \right\}. \quad (2)$$

Compared to its general form, Model (2) uses only one out of two parameters, namely $p_0 \geq 0$, that can be tuned in accordance to the specificity of each approached instance. The other parameter does not affect the optimization results, thus it was removed based on empirically derived conclusions.

In what follows we address multiple objective integer optimization problems, hence we restrict the decision variables x in (1) to take only integer values; and adapt PESA to solve it. The main idea of PESA was to generate one by one well-distributed non-dominated (ND) vectors. Each ND vector, except the extreme ones, was obtained with the help of an hypothetical bound and aimed to cover a gap on the Pareto front. The novelty of our approach is related to the choices of the hypothetical bounds y^0 . Details are provided in Section 3.

To evaluate the performances of our algorithms we used the coverage gap (CG) and inverted generational distance (IGD) as diversity indicators within our experiments. Strengths and weaknesses of a wide class of performance indicators were systematically analyzed in (Audet et al., 2021).

IGD metric is widely used and considered as a trusty performance indicator. It calculates the average distance from uniformly distributed points along the Pareto front (P^*) to discrete Pareto front approximation, A , i.e.

$$IGD(A, P^*) = \frac{\sum_{v \in P^*} d(v, A)}{|P^*|}, \quad (3)$$

where $d(v, A)$ is minimal distance between v and points in A in Euclidean sense. See (Deb and Jain, 2014) for more details.

The coverage gap as performance indicator was introduced in (Ceyhan et al., 2019). Given the discrete Pareto front P and the subset A of P ,

$$\alpha_A(z) = \min_{y \in A} \left(\max_{i=\overline{1,p}} (z_i - y_i) \right) \quad (4)$$

represents a measure of how well the vector z is covered by A . Then, the coverage gap of A is determined by the vector z^* with the worst coverage, i.e. the vector z^* with the greatest value $\alpha_A(z)$. In other words, the coverage gap of A is the value

$$\alpha_A = \alpha_A(z^*), z^* = \arg \max_{z \in P} (\alpha_A(z)). \quad (5)$$

Algorithm 1 Simplified PESA pseudocode (adapted from Stanojevic and Glover, 2020)

Input: An instance of (1) and the number of iterations $nrit$.

- 1: Find marginal solutions and their corresponding extreme ND vectors. Normalize the objective functions.
- 2: Define the first gap to be covered using the extreme ND vectors. Compute its hyper-volume.
- 3: Define the first optimization problem using the first gap, its hyper-volume, the extreme ND vectors and the coefficient vectors used as weights in the aggregation function that yielded the marginal solutions. Include this problem in the list of problems
- 4: **for** $q = 1, nrit$ **do**
- 5: Identify in the list the problem P^0 that has the greatest hyper-volume. Compute its corresponding hypothetical bound y^* and aggregation coefficients c^* .
- 6: Solve (2) with $y^0 = y^*$, $c^0 = c^*$, and derive y^{new} as its solution. Update with y^{new} the list of ND vectors.
- 7: Remove P^0 from the list of problems and insert p new problems with respect to P^0 and y^{new} .
- 8: **end for**

Output: The set of generated ND vectors.

Table 1: Summary of the running times obtained for 2KP instances (Gandibleux and Freville, 2000)

Instance	r	n	$ E_{PF} $	Gandibleux et al., 2000		Our alg.
				Case 1	Case 2	C-TDM
2KP50-11	0.11	50	43	55	78 / 4	1.5620
2KP50-50	0.5	50	51	801	349	3.1002
2KP50-92	0.92	50	2	7	11 / 1	2.7507
2KP100-50	0.5	100	155	-	-	59.4820

3. SOLUTION ALGORITHM

Aiming to solve 2objMIP problems, we exploit the specific shape of the Pareto front brought by the integer components of its ND vectors, and – compared to PESA – conveniently change the manner of choosing the hypothetical bounds to be used in the integer form of the classic TDM (Stanojevic and Glover, 2020) model.

In what follows we present our C-TDM solution approach. C-TDM algorithm uses the integer relaxation of the original problem to define the hypothetical bound y^0 needed in the TDM model (2). Then, we construct gaps and order them with respect to their size, as described in PESA (Stanojevic and Glover, 2020).

The quality of being an anytime algorithm is assured by the inclusion of PESA framework within our solution approach. PESA is briefly described by Algorithm 1.

Each time, the hypothetical bound used by C-TDM to derive a ND vector to the original 2objMIP problem is a ND vector of the Pareto front of the corresponding continual problem obtained by ignoring the integrality constraints on the original decision variables. An approximation of the Pareto front of the continual problem is generated using the classic PESA method. In other words, y^0 is an already generated ND vector to the integer relaxation of the original 2objMIP problem.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

4.1. Bi-objectives KP instances

The first group of experiments were performed on Set 1.A 2KP instances downloaded from (International Society on Multiple Criteria Decision Making, Created : October 1998 — Last update: November 2004), and having the following characteristics: two objectives ($p = 2$), one constraint only ($k = 1$), and several tightness ratio (r). See (Gandibleux and Freville, 2000) where the instances were firstly introduced.

The obtained results are summarized in Table 1:, which shows that our C-TDM algorithm is competitive with the algorithms reported in the literature.

The strength of the C-TDM algorithm can be concluded from the detailed results reported for Instance 2KP50-50. The values of the diversity metrics, IGD and CG, are reported in Table 2:.. Values $IGD = 0$ and $CG = 0$ were obtained after 395 iterations proving that all points on the true Pareto front are obtained.

Analyzing the values reported in Table 2: we draw the following conclusions: (i) the generated ND vectors are well dispersed along the Pareto front; (ii) the quality of the generated approximations to the true Pareto front increases with the number of iterations; and (iii) 300 iterations were needed to generate 50 ND vectors and additional 95 to generate the 51th one.

Figure 1: shows the well-distributed ND vectors generated after a small number of iterations, and the full

Table 2: Instance 2KP50-50

C-TDM				
#it	#NDs	IGD	CG	Time (s)
8	8	18.4153	0.0138	0.1541
32	27	3.1162	0.0028	0.4099
100	39	0.9906	0.0028	0.9181
300	50	0.0608	0.0005	2.4536
395	51	0	0	3.1002

Figure 1: Generated ND vectors on Pareto front of Inst. 2KP50-50 after 8, 32, and 395 iterations respectively

coverage of the Pareto front achieved after 395 iterations. In the first sub-figure can be easily seen that the extrem ND vectors were not disclosed from the beginning.

4.2. Bi-objective MOIP instance

We solved the bi-objective MOIP instance defined by the matrices

$$c = \begin{bmatrix} 6 & 0 & -10 & -23 & 33 & 25 & 27 & -90 & -9 & 27 \\ 92 & 91 & 17 & 75 & 53 & 97 & 31 & -50 & 85 & 93 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 33 & 75 & -22 & 80 & 96 & 76 & 69 & 88 & 60 & 81 \\ 20 & 75 & 5 & 55 & -60 & 39 & 0 & 40 & 86 & 0 \\ 6 & 37 & 86 & 45 & 64 & 85 & 44 & 0 & -89 & 0 \\ 23 & -47 & 26 & 0 & -80 & -81 & -18 & 71 & 0 & 57 \\ 2 & -33 & 35 & 0 & 37 & 17 & -13 & 17 & 100 & 57 \end{bmatrix}, b = \begin{bmatrix} 314 \\ 241 \\ 224 \\ 37 \\ 219 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

Figure 2: shows the derived ND vectors that fully cover the Pareto front.

Figure 2: Generated ND vectors on the Pareto front of the bi-objective MIP problem defined using (6)-(7)

5. CONCLUSION AND FURTHER RESEARCHES

In this study we addressed the 2objMIP problems. Our solution approach is an adaptation of a general procedure proposed in the recent literature to solve continual multiple objective optimization problems. We combined the manner of defining and ordering the sub-sets of the Pareto front (from the continual approach) with a new way of choosing hypothetical bounds to aim. These ways were introduced in accordance to the specific shape of the Pareto fronts of combinatorial optimization problems. We carried out experiments and reported results on bi-objective knapsack and MIP problems. The results obtained for the knapsack problems clearly illustrated that the proposed approach performed well in comparison to the results reported in the literature.

Our plans for future research include wider experiments on larger instances by employing various heuristics for solving single objective mixed-integer programming problems in the framework of our current approach. We will also carry out some more experiments on the same class of problems, aiming to find a way to efficiently tune the problem-specific parameters.

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LITERATURE

- Audet, C., Bigeon, J., Cartier, D., Le Digabel, S., & Salomon, L. (2021). Performance indicators in multiobjective optimization. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 292(2), 397–422. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2020.11.016>
- Cai, X., Hu, M., Gong, D., Guo, Y.-n., Zhang, Y., Fan, Z., & Huang, Y. (2019). A decomposition-based coevolutionary multiobjective local search for combinatorial multiobjective optimization. *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, 49, 178–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.swevo.2019.05.007>
- Ceyhan, G., Köksalan, M., & Lokman, B. (2019). Finding a representative nondominated set for multi-objective mixed integer programs. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 272(1), 61–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2018.06.012>
- Deb, K., & Jain, H. (2014). An evolutionary many-objective optimization algorithm using reference-point-based nondominated sorting approach, part i: Solving problems with box constraints. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 18(4), 577–601. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2013.2281535>
- Deb, K., & Miettinen, K. (2009). A review of nadir point estimation procedures using evolutionary approaches: A tale of dimensionality reduction. In or AUTHOR (Ed.). Proceedings of the Multiple Criterion Decision Making (MCDM-2008) Conference.
- Domínguez-Rios, M. A., Chicano, F., & Alba, E. (2021). Effective anytime algorithm for multiobjective combinatorial optimization problems. *Information Sciences*, 565, 210–228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2021.02.074>
- Ehrgott, M., Gandibleux, X., & Przybylski, A. (2016). Exact methods for multi-objective combinatorial optimisation. In S. Greco, M. Ehrgott, & J. R. Figueira (Eds.), *Multiple criteria decision analysis: State of the art surveys* (pp. 817–850). Springer New York. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-3094-4_19
- Gandibleux, X., & Freville, A. (2000). Tabu search based procedure for solving the 0-1 multiobjective knapsack problem : The two objectives case. *Journal of Heuristics*, 6(3), 361–383.
- International Society on Multiple Criteria Decision Making. (Created : October 1998 — Last update: November 2004). MCDM Numerical Instances Library [Accessed: January 22nd, 2025].
- Ozpeynirci, O., & Koksalan, M. (2010). An exact algorithm for finding extreme supported nondominated points of multiobjective mixed integer programs. *Management Science*, 56(12), 2302–2315.
- Pardalos, P. M., Zilinskas, A., & Zilinskas, J. (2017). *Non-convex multi-objective optimization*. Springer.
- Stanojevic, B., & Glover, F. (2020). A new approach to generate pattern-efficient sets of non-dominated vectors for multi-objective optimization. *Information Sciences*, 530, 22–42.
- Toloo, M., Talatahari, S., Gandomi, A. H., & Rahimi, I. (2022). 1 - multiobjective combinatorial optimization problems: Social, keywords, and journal maps. In M. Toloo, S. Talatahari, & I. Rahimi (Eds.), *Multi-objective combinatorial optimization problems and solution methods* (pp. 1–9). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-823799-1.00010-3>